

THE ROLE OF ONGOING FEEDBACK IN DEVELOPING SOCIOCULTURAL COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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***Abstract.** The authors of the presented scientific article consider in detail the model of formation of socio-cultural competence among students of a pedagogical university, noting its necessity and exceptional benefit both for the study and practical application of a foreign language, and for the comprehensive and harmonious development of personality.*

***Keywords.** Socio-cultural competence, socio-cultural approach, model of competence formation, linguistic and cultural reading, a set of exercises and tasks, organizational and pedagogical aspects of learning.*

Introduction. The purpose of the study is to theoretically substantiate and practically verify the model of formation of socio-cultural competence of students in the field of training "Pedagogical education" in the process of teaching linguistic and cultural reading in English. The relevance of the problem under study. The relevance of our work lies in the fact that today the main task of an educational institution of higher education is education within the framework of the discipline "Foreign language" is the formation and development of students' socio-cultural aspect in learning a foreign language. The teacher should not only teach the language in its "pure form" (vocabulary, phonetics, grammar), but also give students knowledge about the culture of the country of the studied language, its history, outstanding people, traditions, worldview of its people, etc.

Main Part. The background knowledge system can be represented as follows:

- 1) culture of information ("Small Culture"), which includes information from history, geography, everyday life, etc.;
- 2) culture of values ("Big Culture"), consisting of authentic literature, music, various folklore works, painting, theater, cinema, etc.;
- 3) a culture of behavior, implying moral and etiquette norms, accepted norms of communication of both verbal and non-verbal types among this ethnic group.

The culture of values can and should be used as one of the components of the content of the previously discussed linguistic and cultural reading for non-linguistic universities. The task of the students in this case will be to identify the linguistic and cultural lexemes found in the text and to compile comments explaining the specific concepts of another culture. The theoretical tradition of Vygotsky and the sociocultural school hold that the origins of consciousness are social. This means that we become who we are through participating in the communities around us. Learning and identity are therefore inseparable, such that 'Learning implies becoming a different person (and) involves the construction of identity (Lave and Wenger, 1991:53). However, rather than reflecting any 'essential' character or personality, identities are multiple, performed and continually reconstructed through engagement with others. Ricoeur (1991) agrees that mediation of cultural signs is at the heart of how we give meaning to our lives, and sees our sense of self as constituted through the narratives we co-construct in our everyday lives. The self is therefore a 'figured self' where identity is created through narrative interpretations (Ricoeur, 1991:199). These involve the intersection of a sense of permanence of oneself over time (idem/sameness) and a sense of faithfulness to oneself in terms of keeping one's promises (ipse/selfhood).

Conclusion. The theoretical justification and practical verification of the developed model confirm that the effective formation and further development of socio-cultural competence in teaching linguistic and cultural reading creates a high level of motivation for further study and use of a foreign language for personal and professional purposes. The result of this training is a graduate of a pedagogical

university with a high level of socio-cultural competence development, which allows adequate and effective use of language in communication for the purposes of both a deeper knowledge of the country of the studied language and its people.

REFERENCES

1. Engeström, Y. (2000) from individual action to collective activity and back: developmental work research as an interventionist methodology, in: P. Luff, J. Hindmarsh & C. Heath (Eds.) *Workplace studies: Recovering work practice and informing system design*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
2. Grayling, A. (2017). *Future education and skills: Education 2030: Reflections on transformative competencies 2030*. Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development. [https://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/contact/EDUEDPC \(2017\) 16-ANN5.pdf](https://www.oecd.org/education/2030-project/contact/EDUEDPC%20(2017)%2016-ANN5.pdf).
3. Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development. (2018). *OECD future of education and skills 2030* [https://www.oecd.org/education/2030?E2030%20Position%20Paper%\(05.04.2018\).pdf](https://www.oecd.org/education/2030?E2030%20Position%20Paper%(05.04.2018).pdf).
4. Ricoeur, P. (1991) *Narrative Identity*, in: D. Wood (Ed.) *On Paul Ricoeur. Narrative and Interpretation*, London: Routledge.